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**Serhiy Korol¹, Vitaliy Korol¹, Mateusz Kamionka²,
Anna Zinchenko¹**

¹ Sumy State University, Sumy, Ukraine

² Pedagogical University of Cracow, Cracow, Poland

Leisure Management at the Educational Institutions of the Labour Reserves System During the Post-War Recovery of Ukraine (1945-1950)

Abstract: *Introduction.* The study is relevant due to considering of socio-cultural life arrangement positive and negative domestic experience at the current reformation of professional education in Ukraine. *Purpose and methods.* The aim of the article lies in the analysis of arrangement peculiarities of students' leisure at professional schools in the period of the Post-war Recovery of Ukraine (1945-1950). The study used methods include general scientific (analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, typology, abstraction) and special (problem-chronological, comparative, systematic, retrospective, hermeneutics and content-analysis elements) methods. *Results.* The research reveals that the extra-curricular activity and organized leisure time of students at labour reserves educational establishments, primarily, were additionally political-ideologically and military-physically oriented. It also used the principles of authoritative pedagogy. *Conclusions.* The scientific novelty of the research results is that for the first time the analysis, classification and characterization of specific types of students' free time organization were made, as well as efficiency of the motivation and control means of leisure arrangement model was evaluated. The practical significance of the results is reflected in the presentation to modern educators and students of the leisure organization peculiarities in the post-war period, which has an important pedagogical and educational role and can be used in the preparation of specialists in the specialty "Management of Socio-Cultural Activities".

Keywords: management, control, planning, administration, leisure arrangement, professional education, extracurricular activity.

1. Introduction

The problem formulation. Modern researchers define leisure as a set of activities, carried out at the free time to meet specific physical, intellectual, social and cultural needs. In the broad sense, leisure is identified as free time, that is off-duty time (work and chores) (Ruchka, 2008).

Investigators distinguish the following types of leisure: individual culture consumption (literature, TV programs, etc.); public and entertaining culture consumption (theatre, cinema, popular science lectures, sports events); communication (family, relatives, friends); physical training, sports and tourism; passive rest (walks, environment contemplation for no specific purpose); creative amateur activities (art studios, scientific circles, etc.) (Tkachuk, 2015, pp. 131-132). The nature of leisure is one of the key indicators of an individual's well-being level, cultural and educational development, social communication, as well as physical and psychological state.

For a long time, scientists paid special attention to the organization of leisure activities of the young generation at educational institutions. Proper leisure was not only a recreational goal but also a part of the pedagogical process, used to instill values of society, nurture the necessary qualities of character and many-sided personal development of children and adolescents. Modern socio-cultural management development at educational institutions demands from us, we are inevitably forced to look back into the past to take advantage of past experiences or to avoid past unfortunate mistakes in this field.

At present, there is a profound reform of the professional education field in Ukraine. The organization of extracurricular work in relevant institutions improves as well. It should be noted that until recently, national professional education remained a direct descendant of the Soviet system of state labor reserves, inheriting both the traditions and principles of its work and many different disadvantages. Therefore, it is very relevant to study the issue of organizing leisure in post-war educational reserves, because knowing the roots of the troubles makes it much easier to solve them during the current transformations.

State study of the problem. The system of state labor reserves was a centralized structure for professional training during the 1940s–1950s. It involved industrial schools, vocational schools and some similar sectoral educational institutions. Labor reserves were semi-military. Institutions of state labor reserves involved both enlistees and forcibly mobilized youth, and the runoff was considered a criminal offence in the 1940s.

Soviet historians created the largest selection of works on the history of the labor reserves system. To some extent, these works also touched upon the issue of organizing leisure for the student of vocational education institutions. However, the studies were written under the rigid dictate of official communist ideology, responding to the views of the authorities on historical events. Scientists in the Soviet Union forcibly presented not a real-world picture of the past events, but rather a rosy picture, when the teaching, the way of life, and the leisure of students-reservists were almost perfect thanks to sharp management. The tendency of Soviet-era works always compels to take them critically.

The modern Ukrainian historiography of labour reserves educational institutions formed along with the state independence. First of all, O. Bombandiorova (2000) devoted her PhD thesis to this issue. The author identified many significant shortcomings in the educational work of schools and colleges. It was emphasized that the financial support of most professional education institutions in Ukraine did not correspond to the official norms.

M. Loboda (2012) considered the role of schools and colleges of state labor reserves in the formation of labor force during the reconstruction of heavy industry in Ukraine. L. Khoynatska (2003) investigated the labor reserves system, especially the activity of training institutions for mechanical engineering personnel. Her study also gave a thorough assessment of the social and youth policies of the Soviet government.

The works of I. Likarchuk (1998) and A. Seletskyi (2012) describe the reconstruction of professional education pedagogical system of the 1940s – 1950s. They consider the organizational and pedagogical subject and forms of training as well as state labor reserves management methods under the command-and-administration system.

The studies of H. Holysh (2005), I. Hridina and N. Kasianova (2008) also draw attention, as they give the analysis to the issues like the effects of war on juvenile citizens, the current orphanage and homelessness. The scientists also underlined the significant role of the labor reserve system in overcoming these problems during the post-war period.

O. Yankovska's (2014) study on the state social policy in the second half of the 1940s–mid 1950s, as well as its perceptions by ordinary residents of Ukraine, is worth attention. The author revealed the horrific destitution, half-starved existence, hard work of young people called up or who voluntarily entered the industrial schools.

V. Baran (2003) and L. Kovpak (2007) created complex studies of the socio-political and cultural and educational development of post-war Ukraine as a background for the labor reserves system.

The topic of labor reserves is also reflected at the regional level. In particular, N. Shypik (2012), P. Dobrov and Ya. Ovchynnikova (2008) investigated the training and working conditions of the Donbass reservists. V. Korol (2015) studied the activity of labor reserves in the western regions of Ukraine as well.

In 2004, a unique encyclopedic edition “Professional Education of Ukraine of the XX Century” was published. It contains essays on the history of professional education in each region of Ukraine together with biographical information of prominent figures in this field. However, the edition authors were mostly not scientists but amateur educators and ethnographers (Nychkalo, 2004).

Western researchers, however, have long been unable to give a thorough analysis of the activities of the Soviet professional education system because of the limited access to objective information sources during the Cold War.

The active study of the Soviet labor reserves by Western scientists began only after the Soviet Union collapsed when foreign scientists gained access to its archives. First of all, the work of the British scientist D. Filzer stands out. The researcher discovered the Soviet policy of mobilizing young people to labor reserves under conditions of the post-war reconstruction as well as the socio-economic and demographic deformities it led to (Filtzer, 2002). Separately, the researcher studied the state of health care and epidemiological measures related to displacement for long distances of the called young people (Filtzer, 2010).

O. Kucherenko (2012), a British of Slavic origin, in her work addresses the history of the state labor reserves system in the context of the Soviet children life investigation during World War II. The scientist emphasizes that labor reserves became a means of mass use of youth work and socialization under the requirements of the totalitarian system.

In general, modern scientific literature on the history of professional education reflects most of the key aspects of the labor reserve educational system. However, practically all works only slightly touch on the issue of leisure management of students-reservists and managing extracurricular life in professional education institutions. It seems so far even paradoxical, given considerable attention to a retrospective study of socio-cultural activity management and its development. For example, the background, nature and stages of the formation of a modern management system of society's socio-cultural component are studied at the general theoretical level (Martynyshyn & Kovalenko, 2018). The origin of the mechanistic management culture, its theory and history were studied together with the identification of its basic determinants (Kovalenko, 2019).

Among specific historical studies of leisure activities of different social groups during the socialist era the works of L. Siegelbaum (1999), V. Girginov (2017), D. Crowley and S. Reid (2010) cover the issue of leisure management

of the Soviet workers. The works of J. Zaida (2014), N. Khomenko (2009), G. Tsipursky (2016) focused on the leisure of students of higher education institutions.

Unresolved issues. We should note in equal measure the lack of a modern special study that would objectively cover leisure activities in professional education institutions, the real state of student recreation and extracurricular activities, as well as a comprehensive analysis of the state labour system socio-cultural features in post-war Ukraine. So far, a detailed study of the planning, managing and monitoring the cultural and leisure component of professional education institutions in the extreme conditions of rebuilding a devastated economy state is of great necessity.

2. Purpose and methods

The purpose of the article. The purpose of the study is to analyze the peculiarities of the students' leisure arrangement at the Soviet professional education institutions. The chronological framework was defined as 1945 – 1950 – the period of post-war economic recovery. The period is chosen due to the most active development of the respective branch, giving it the function of authoritarian militarized education, not peculiar to professional education.

The methodological basis of the study. The basic principles used include the principles of objectivity, system, historicism, comprehensiveness and anthropological studies. The principle of historicism involved considering specific historical circumstances of the relevant time, the events interconnection and interdependence, understanding the causes, time, and place of the event. There is the principle of objectivity ensured relation on real facts, making impartial assessments, approaching sources and historiographical material critically. The principles of system of the socio-economic, political, moral and psychological factors of the socio-cultural life impact at the labor reserves institutions. The anthropological studies principle accentuated the human-centered nature of the proposed study, given the position that only humanism as a philosophical category and socio-cultural phenomenon of governance could create a reliable methodological base for building a humane society (Kovalenko et al., 2019).

Research methods. Common scientific methods were used: analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, classification, abstraction, etc. They contributed to identification of the general and special in the structure of the educational institutions studied and their students' leisure arrangement.

Some specific methods have also been applied: problem-chronological – to distinguish several rather narrow historical aspects within the theme; comparative-historical – to identify regional differences in extracurricular activities in in-

stitutions of state labor reserves; historical and systematic – to determine the mutual influence of the socio-political situation in the state and the nature of students-labor reservists' leisure; retrospective – to evaluate the socio-cultural life of professional education institutions of the relevant historical period from the point of view of the present time; methods of hermeneutics and content analysis – for interpretation and characterization of research sources.

Research information base. The source database involves two groups: published sources and archival documents.

Most of the published sources on this issue appeared during the Soviet period. These are directories of post-war regulations and thematic collections of historical documents. Important information related to the labor reserves educational institutions activity is provided by periodicals of the time studied. The most informative is the journal “Industrial Training”. It was the main printed body of the state labor reserves system in the Soviet Union. This issue published training programs and guidelines, covered the life of professional education institutions.

As for *archival sources*, they all belong to the category of official record-keeping documents appeared during the state institutions and organizations activity of the time. Information was used from the Central State Archive of highest authorities and administration of Ukraine, as well as from State Archive of Public Associations of Ukraine and state archives of Lugansk, L'viv, Odesa and Sumy regions.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Public ideologically oriented activities

In addition to education and training, one of the main tasks of the labour reserve system was to foster future young workers under the requests of the state. Ideological and political components comprised the major part and had to be delivered both in the classes and beyond them. The Soviet authorities assumed that any school activity should have promoted the materialistic world-view and the so-called “communist morality” among the youth.

Professor *I. Kairov*, an active member of the Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of the Soviet Union, specialized in the theoretical development of the ideological education methodology for labor reserves system in the 1940s. He identified the following methodical extracurricular forms of its implementation: revolutionary celebrations and other public events, lectures, discussions, student clubs and Komsomol organizations, home reading and reading conferences, student publishing activities (billposters or print small newspapers).

He emphasized that the task of teaching staff during any extracurricular work was “to constantly disclose the political essence of historical and current events to young people” (Kairov, 1947, pp. 4-5). In other words, the students’ free time, their leisure and recreation have been inevitably steeped in ideological treatment.

In general, the daily schedule at schools of the state labour reserves system was planned almost minute by minute and, as a rule, was carried out with military rigor. Wakeup at 6.30. Then morning gymnastics, room cleaning, roll call and breakfast and off to study. Classes lasted from 8.30 a.m. to 4.30 p.m. with a one-hour lunch break. Dinner was at 6.30 p.m. The time between classes and dinner intended leisure and cultural work. Therefore, youth leisure was limited to two hours on weekdays. After dinner, labour reservists had to do homework for an hour and a half, and after the evening line and roll call, they went to bed. The bed-time signal was at 9.45 p.m. Labour reservists lived according to this schedule six days a week. Sunday was officially a day off and considered free time for students (Rozofarov, 1950, pp. 74-75).

Usually, students could have left on a Sunday or a public holiday. It was even allowed to leave school on Saturday evening or holiday eve for visiting relatives. Headmaster or hall monitor only granted the leave. It was issued as an established release document, containing information about the student, reasons for the leave and the exact time of return. Students, allowed to leave, were required to come to the hall monitor dressed in uniform and obtain a release document. On return from the leave, the student had to report back to the hall monitor and hand him in the release document. The hall monitor examined the returnee and made a note of his return to the roll (Rozofarov, 1950, pp. 76-77).

Student leisure management at the labor reserve institutions was obligatory under control of local Komsomol organizations. The latter included most of the students, young people and educators. A whole department of vocational and factory training schools appeared under the Komsomol Central Committee of Ukraine, which had to administrate the work of its structure at the labour reserves institutions (Otchet o Rabote Otdela, 1948, p. 2).

Educational institutions held thematic public lectures at least once a month. These events took place in “red corners”, clubs of educational establishments or enterprises. Along with the teachers from schools or labor reserves institutions, the lectures were also delivered by qualified regular lecturers-propagandists from City or Region Committees of Communist Party, Komsomol Committees, employees from local higher education establishments and administrators of labour reserves departments. Several thousand of such events took place at the educational institutions of the state labour reserves system of Ukraine every year. According to official reports, they covered the entire learning community of the Republic.

The lectures topics were mostly political. “The Life and Work of Lenin”, “Lenin and Stalin – The Red Army Founders and Leaders”, “Comrade Stalin and His Patronage of Labour Reserves”, “The Komsomol During the War”, “The Nuremberg Trials” and other were common topics for lectures. Naturalistic (“The Origin of Life on Earth”, “Is There an End of the World?”, “Atomic Energy”), historical-patriotic (“Great Russian Commanders”, “Nationalism of a Soviet Person”) or moral and psychological (“Friendship and Comradeship”, “Morality of the Soviet Youth”) were less common topics. However, those lectures still had to conform to the Marxist doctrine and involved a political component (Otchet Respublikanskogo Upravlenija, 1945, pp. 37-38).

Young people, though, often perceived these lectures, oversaturated with official ideology, with utter indifference. Thus, in June 1949, the secretary of the Voroshylovgrad Regional Committee of the Komsomol of Ukraine, during his speech at the regional scientific-pedagogical conference underlined: “There are no complaints about the number of lectures. But this activity does not take into account the age and educational level of students. They are not interested. There are no lectures that would rouse interest among our youth” (Stenogramma Pervoj, 1949, p. 11). Labour reserves students attended lectures only under the administration constraint, as a rule.

The biographies of “great leaders”, “brilliant teachers of the proletariat” and the rulers of the Soviet state – V. Lenin and J. Stalin – formed a rich source for the ideological and political education of young people. Studying the exaggerated official versions of their lives turned into a means of establishing a moral ideal, an example for adolescents, as well as an instrument for maintaining the cult of personality in a totalitarian society. The study of the Bolshevik Party, its history and achievements, also had great importance for the systematic ideological treatment of youth (Kairov, 1947, pp. 4-5).

The educational establishments created so-called “optional” sections according to the instructions of the Center, each specialized in the extra-curricular study of their own thematic area, like: the biography of V. Lenin, the biography of J. Stalin, history of the Communist Party, the Constitution of the Soviet Union, the statute of the Leninist Young Communist League of the Soviet Union, Five-Year Plan IV, etc.

Sections had to meet weekly on schedule. Their head relied on a teacher of political education or an assistant director on cultural and mass work. At group meetings, reports were presented and related issues were discussed. School administrations usually created as many sections as possible and recorded most of their students in order to improve the performance of their institutions. The popularity of this leisure activity among the youth was a pure

fiction, and membership a mere formality. It was impossible to hold such session regularly as it would immediately paralyze other types of extracurricular activities in the physical realm.

Meetings with foremost workers, skilled enterprise personnel, the best alumni, war heroes, holders of the orders and other guests of unquestioned authority were also among the types of mass events at schools and colleges of the state labour reserve system. The guests grandly addressed students, presented the institution and received as well symbolic gifts, communicated with the youth informally, answering their questions. Such measures were of great importance for several reasons: nurturing the typical Soviet patriotism and ephemeral “proletarian consciousness”, cultivating a passion for the future profession, adopting life experience of those among the older generation, who were considered prominent in the times.

Some meetings were of high impact. For example, in 1945 S. Kovpak, twice the Hero of the Soviet Union, was the guest at the Kyiv Vocational School No. 2 and spoke about the creation of his guerrilla squad and struggle against the German occupiers (*Otchet Respublikanskogo Upravlenija*, 1945, p. 40). In 1948 P. Voronko, the former guerrilla commander and later the famous poet and public figure, in the same way, visited Putivl Special Vocational School No. 44 (*Yevstratov*, 1948, p. 4).

National holidays and significant anniversaries like Red Army and Fleet Day, International Women's Day (particularly at institutions with female students), Victory Day, the anniversary of the Great October Socialist Revolution, birthdays of V. Lenin and J. Stalin and more were celebrated at the labour reserves institutions with distinctive attention. October 2 was the direct professional holiday of the state labour reserves system, in fact, its foundation date, that later was called “Tradesman Day” (*Rozofarov*, 1950, pp. 138-140).

Educational institutions, where student prepared for certain industries (e.g. mining, metallurgy, construction) often celebrated professional holidays at their responsibility. In addition to the official lineups, and heads' speeches of the facility managers and guests of honor, the celebration usually included concerts and sports competitions.

3.2. Cultural and physical activities

Educational institutions opened libraries, clubs and “red corners” had reading rooms as well, regularly supplied with literature by booksellers. Librarians had to report systematically on the literature promotion campaigns at methodological meetings with the head of an educational institution. So far, educational institutions annually planned “book weeks” (*Rozofarov*, 1950, p. 141).

Each “red corner” at the dormitories should have provided board games (chess, checkers, dominoes, lotto), musical instruments, and in the absence of a library also books, newspapers and magazines. At the same time, gambling (especially playing cards for stakes) was strictly forbidden.

Satiric billposters with jokes, caricatures and cartoons revealing negative aspects of school life were widely used to affect offenders and careless students, to improve the discipline as well as the success of educational and production activities. Such publications were called by analogy with the most famous at the time relevant all-Union magazine “Crocodile”. However, in Western Ukraine billposters were titled as “Pepper” in line with the Ukrainian satirical issue (*Otchet o kul'turno-massovoj*, 1947, pp. 3, 5).

Usually, billposters were eagerly published almost at every institution of the state labour reserves system. The prevailing number of satirical newspapers over the analogical issues of serious ideological and political nature particularly indicates their extremely high popularity. Thus, in 1945 were issued only about 4.9 thousand ordinary newspapers, whether satirical “crocodiles” and “peppers” reached the number of 6.5 thousand (*Otchet Respublikanskogo Upravljenija*, 1945, pp. 41-42).

In order to direct students' creative activity to more solid and profound assimilation of their knowledge, colleges and industrial schools arranged technical clubs and rooms for young engineers and inventors. Along with that, such leisure activity was appropriate for the accomplishment. Thus, radio-engineering clubs got specific tasks of installing a loudspeaker radio system at their schools or affiliated institutions and organizations (orphanages, collective farms).

Deputy directors on educational work or senior masters of the labour reserves schools monitored the work of technical clubs. The same people were responsible for so-called “technical propaganda” (achievements popularization of domestic technology and industry) through lectures, talks, student conferences and exhibitions of the best products made by reservists and their masters of industrial training (*Rozofarov*, 1950, p. 141).

Amateur art activities the pride, as a rule, was a pride of each labor reserves institution. The youth, seeking for entertainment and creative expression, created various orchestras and choirs, and other students engaged in recitation and dramatic arts. Students constantly held concerts according to the developed plans at clubs, basic enterprises, local hospitals, surrounding collective farms and recruitment locations for education at industrial schools of Donbas.

During the mobilization campaigns, amateur participants travelled with propaganda teams to different places, demonstrating their talents and urging youngsters to join the labor reserves educational system. Sometimes these amateur artists with their concert programs were invited to perform on the radio, and they became real celebrities in their city (*Protokoly Obshhjih Sobranij*, 1947, p. 6).

After the war, the regional departments of labor reserves in big cities built their own institutional palaces of culture. Often, apart from housing student art groups, they also hosted amateur art festivals of all regional educational institutions. For example, Odessa region labor reservists organized such festivals and contests in their palace of culture annually in June and July (Plany Raboty, 1946, pp. 11-13).

However, the repertoire had to be controlled by the Komsomol. Amateur art was required to be planned with and hold the “deep ideological content”. However, students, already tired of political indoctrination, often preferred folklore and entertaining songs and plays instead of serious Soviet and Komsomol works. Local directories turned a blind eye to that. The regional committees of the Komsomol of Ukraine, though, after certain “orders”, made the Komsomol local departments fight that “lack of principles” through the critics and admonitions.

In fact, along with that struggle, another real social danger was spreading, though intentionally unmentioned to the general public. The criminal subculture began to spread among the students. That was especially the case in Donbas and Kryvbas regions, with most of the labour reserves schools of Ukraine, and a significant number of criminals working at local mines. Rogue songs and poetry with speaking titles like “Thief”, “Jailers”, “Letter from Kolyma” etc. were gaining popularity. Spreading of shameful songs with vulgar, obscene content became another disaster (Stenogramma Pervoj, 1949, p. 21).

Some officials began to beat the alarm. In 1949 one of the latter publicly stated: “The Komsomol did not become the soul of mass culture work in the labor reserves ... Shame on the Komsomol members. They couldn't get interested, spark our youth!” (Stenogramma Pervoj, 1949, pp. 40-41). But the truth was that those totalitarian methods of restriction and amateur activity direct control could have only created a false wrapper, that repelled most students with its insincerity.

From time to time, students were organized for movies, theatres or museums cult. Regional cinema departments arranged the work of mobile film stations for the college and school students. Also, according to the instructions of the Ministry of Cinematography, special price-privileged cinema sessions for labour reservists were held at city cinemas once a week. A well-known case was when an educational institution purchased a film projection unit at its own expense and regularly showed free films to its students (Medvid, 1948, p. 4).

In October 1945, a film festival “The Komsomol and Youth at Battlefield and Work” was organized in Kharkiv for industrial school's students and colleges. Heroic films like the current masterpieces “The Great Life”, “Alexander Nevsky”, “At Six in the Afternoon After the War” etc. have been screened at the Dzerzhinsky Cinema for eight days. There were lectures and amateur groups

performing for young people in the lobby before the film sessions. According to official estimates, in total, 15 thousand people attended the event (Otchet Respublikanskogo Upravljenija, 1945, p. 43). It was considered an example to follow.

In the first postwar years, though, along with the Soviet films, the so-called “trophy films” were shown, mainly German or American entertaining and adventure pictures. They were extremely popular among the youth as they distracted from the hard reality at least for a while. The same was with the labour reservists. But for organized trips to “idle” foreign cinema, in addition to the gratitude of the students, however, the administration of institutions inevitably received serious troubles from the city or regional management of the state labour reserves for arranging film shows with “lack of principles” (Stenogramma Pervoj, 1949, p. 24).

Any cultural outing always meant an additional responsibility for the teaching staff. Therefore, most employees were not eager to make it more often. All the more indeed scary cases have happened since that. Thus, in 1949, in the Voroshylovgrad (Lugansk) region, during a culture outing of the students from the Mining Industrial School No. 53, a fight broke out between labour reservists and workers, one of the latter killed. Shortly afterwards, a group of drunken companions of a murdered worker stormed into the school dormitory and made real mayhem (Spravka o proverke, 1949, p. 2).

In 1943 the Voluntary Sports Association “Labour Reserves” was founded to promote physical education and sports activities at schools and colleges of the system of state labour reserves, with its centers almost at every educational institution. Under the auspices of that sports association, many sports clubs operated at schools and colleges. The most popular were games (football, volleyball), athletics, as well as skiing and shooting. Special facilities and venues were equipped to organize the training. Trade-union committees allowed to use their gyms and stadiums as well (Rozofarov, 1950, pp. 140-142).

Students regularly participated in competitions both among members of their sports society and at championships of different levels – from city and district to all-Union. At the same time, the activity of the “Labor Reserves” sports association although provided the mass public, but not quality. The overwhelming majority of members could not demonstrate mere athletic achievements. Only several individuals received athletic titles (the figure “2.5 % of the total number of members” is mentioned). Lack of professional trainers, inventory and material resources led to poor quality of training (Stenogramma Pervoj, 1949, p. 27). However, the Soviet authorities were more likely to need not strong potential soldiers other than strong athletes. First of all, the sports association had to prepare young people for completing physical standards of the “Ready for Work and Defense” complex.

Factory training and vocational schools also had groups where boys and girls studied different military specialities (snipers, machine gunners, mortars, etc.). The patriotism and heroic enthusiasm of the war children fueled by active agitation provided enough of enlistees. Military leaders and physical education instructors conducted the training. The drill preparation was of great importance. Ever since the end of 1944, internal and quarterly regional labour reservists' inspection parades were held monthly, and often together with marching songs contests. The directors and administration from the regional departments of the state labor reserves performed the role of the jury (Priказы Nachal'nika, 1944, pp. 7-8, 56).

What was the alternative to the arranged leisure at the institutions of the labour reserve system?

Informal, self-contained leisure often gave with internal schedule disturbances. It sometimes took socially dangerous forms. It happened that the students (usually boys) drank, inevitably accompanying that by bullying, fights, immoral behavior.

On the other hand, self-arranged leisure could have been socially adequate, as well. Village boys and girls, when in a city, used to go to the traditional get-togethers in the street, with talks, jokes and folk songs. However, according to one of the Donbas Labour Reserves leaders, those "backward village parties" were considered a threat to the Komsomol education. Therefore, street gatherings were forbidden with students sent to clubs and "red corners" (Spravki o Rabote, 1950, pp. 9-10).

Many youngsters were harvesting mushrooms and berries or fishing during those hungry post-war years. They had to leave school without permission in order to go to a forest or river. However, the institution administration, instead of fighting that, took it under control. The students were forced to donate the trophies to the "common pot" in the dining room. In 1946, 300 kg of berries, 120 kg of mushrooms and 300 kg of fish were collected in Sumy region (Otchet o Dejatel'nosti, 1946, p. 38).

Despite the active atheistic propaganda, not all students of state labor reserve institutions became "godless". Some students secretly wore crosses, prayed and skipped schools to attend church. The issue of religion was particularly acute for the forcibly mobilized young people of regions only recently annexed by the Soviet Union (in particular, Western Ukraine) since the latter had brought up in believing Christian families (Korol, 2015, p. 129).

Some officials of the state labour reserves system were rather interested in keeping students' good psychological condition and positive mood than to fight with faith in God. Thus, in 1948, the head of the Krasnolutsk City Department of Labour Reserves arranged organized service attendance in order

to stop students' unauthorized church visits. On Sunday, those interested lined up and went to church with the master in charge. Subsequently, such an approach to the extracurricular work of the said official came under extreme criticism by the Central Committee of the Komsomol of Ukraine in a special report on the political education of labour reservists (*Spravki po Proverke*, 1948, p. 4).

4. Conclusions

The analysis of the specific domestic experience of managing the socio-cultural life and leisure organization at the professional education institutions of the said chronological period allows to make the following conclusions:

1. The organization of extra-curricular life of young people of the labor reserves system institutions involved semi-military principles of personal development and the daily routine of labour reservists was strictly regulated.

2. Extracurricular work and arranged students' leisure at the labor reserves educational institutions primarily directed at additional political-ideological and military-physical education of the mobilized youth, involving the principles of authoritarian pedagogy.

3. Student leisure activities were ideological and patriotic and promoted a militaristic spirit at professional schools and colleges.

4. The students ambiguously expressed their attitude to socio-cultural life management in the professional education system. Despite the apparent loyalty to the nature of mass education, the total control and excessive ideologization during the leisure activities made it unattractive for the youth.

5. Informal, self-organized leisure activities, despite its nature, was considered to be harmful. As a result, it was prohibited and fought by the state labor reserves administrations.

Scientific novelty of the obtained results. The scientific originality of the obtained results comprises a thorough study of the students' leisure arrangement at the system of state labor reserves, which has not been studied so far. For the first time, an objective analysis, classification and characterization of certain youth leisure activities were accomplished. The motivation and control means efficiency of the management model of that time were thoroughly evaluated as well.

The practical significance of the results obtained. The practical significance of the obtained results is manifested in the presentation of the totalitarian age leisure arrangement peculiarities to the modern pedagogical practitioners and students, that is of pedagogical and educational value. The results also may be useful for the preparation of specialists in the specialty "Management of Socio-Cultural Activities".

Prospects for further scientific exploration in this direction. Further scientific investigation perspective of the issue may involve a comparative study of the cultural and leisure activities and its arrangement specifics as well for different categories of the Soviet youth: schoolchildren, labour reservists, students, young workers and collective farmers, conscripts, etc.

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Information about the Authors:

Serhiy Korol, Assoc. Professor, PhD, Sumy State University, 2 Rimsky-Korsakov Str., Sumy 40007, Ukraine; e-mail: korol.sumdu@gmail.com; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5949-4699> (corresponding author)

Vitaliy Korol, Lecturer, PhD, Sumy State University, Sumy, Ukraine; e-mail: zholud.zholud@gmail.com; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5805-1415>

Mateusz Kamionka, Research Scientist, PhD, Pedagogical University of Cracow, Cracow, Poland; e-mail: mattkamionka@gmail.com; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7316-145X>

Anna Zinchenko, Assist. Lecturer, Sumy State University, Sumy, Ukraine; e-mail: annascent@gmail.com; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5672-2331>